

The 21st Century Guitar Conference 2021: Participants' reactions

 Steve Goss is with **Milton Mermikides** and **2 others**.
27 March · 🌐

Last week, Amy Brandon and Rita Torres organised an incredible guitar research event - the 21c Guitar Conference live-streamed from Lisbon in Portugal. Everything is now online, papers, concerts, round tables, etc. Go to www.21cguitar.com to access everything. Guitar research has grown exponentially over the last few years and I am proud to be associated with the people who have made a real difference. Thanks to Amy, Rita, Michelle and the whole 21c Guitar team, for a memorable and important contribution to guitar research.

 Milton Mermikides
27 March · 🌐

The 21st Century Guitar Conference 2021 - shifted from Lisbon to online - was truly remarkable, and what guitar (and in fact all) academic conferences should strive for: rich in content, inclusive, diverse, embracing all genres and modes of music-making, and with direct access and exchange with all participants. I've never experienced a conference so well organised (with precision, thought, but remarkable relaxation) by [Amy Brandon](#), [Rita Torres](#) with great tech from Michelle and team. I really recommend searching through the 5 days of presentations and events. Congratulations and thanks all round.

 Jason Noble
26 March · 🌐

What an amazing and inspiring week at the [21st Century Guitar Conference](#)! Congratulations and thank you to [Amy Brandon](#) and [Rita Torres](#) for organizing such a wonderful conference, and to [Michelle Elle](#) for an impeccable job managing the tech. Special thanks to [Steve Cowan](#) and [Michael Ibsen](#) for their amazing recordings of my pieces that were featured at this event. Wish we could all celebrate in person, but given the circumstances, I think it was a tremendous success.

 Marco Ramelli
29 March · 🌐

Last week, I gave a lecture on Gerhard's music at the [21st Century Guitar Conference](#), one of the most fabulous guitar research events perfectly organised by [Amy Brandon](#) and [Rita Torres](#). For the occasion, I decided to record my composition Fantasia written for Andrea Dieci, which is vaguely inspired by Gerhard's music. I recorded a new version of the piece, longer and with a second part that makes the composition more complex. I only had two days to study and record the piece. The result is a very impromptu version in which some parts are practically improvised, but I thought it was aligned with the conference theme. Here you can listen to the complete piece, and at this link, you can instead listen to my lecture (it starts at 2:12:00) <https://youtu.be/HQ8OqaXia3I?t=7964>

 Michael Ibsen
28 March · 🌐

So excited to share this video of [Jason Noble](#)'s 'Shadow Prism' which I made and was premiered this past week in the [The 21st Century Guitar Conference 2021](#). Thanks to [Amy Brandon](#) and [Rita Torres](#) for organizing an awesome conference!

I am so grateful to my friend [Steve Cowan](#) for collaborating with Jason on the creation of this piece, and being such a champion for new Canadian music. Because of hearing him play this piece and others like it I've learned how rich the repertoire of new Canadian guitar music is, and it's an honour to make my own recording of this groundbreaking work 😊

 Rich Perks
27 March · 🌐

Had a wonderful time presenting research (with [Tom Williams](#)) and forming part of the closing roundtable on Improvisation (alongside [Jonathan](#), [Trevor](#), [Francesca](#), [Patrick](#) & [Diageo](#)) at [The 21st Century Guitar](#) conference yesterday. Many congratulations and special thanks to [Amy](#), [Rita](#), [Michelle](#) (and all involved) for putting on a week of thoroughly interesting, exciting and inspiring presentations! Here's to the next one (hopefully in person)!!

 Tolgahan Çoğulu is with **Agustín Castilla-Ávila** and **4 others**.
24 March · 🌐

Dün, Portekiz'de düzenlenen The 21st Century Guitar konferansında Extended Techniques & Microtonality panelinde çok değerli besteciler ve gitaristlerle beraberdik. Konferans cumaya kadar sürüyor. Canlı izleyebilirsiniz.

Such an honor to chair the Extended Techniques & Microtonality panel at the 21st Century Guitar Conference with great composers and guitarists. The conference ends on Friday. Don't miss it! Such a historical event.

With [Agustín Castilla-Ávila](#), [Juergen Ruck](#), [Michael Kudirka](#), [Mauricio Carrasco](#), [Pascale Criton](#), [Rita Torres](#)

 Rich Perks
22 March · 🌐

Very excited to be presenting research at The 21st Century Guitar - Unconventional Approaches to Performance, Composition and Research, collaborating with [Tom Williams](#). I'll also be part of the closing roundtable panel discussion on Improvisation. Congratulations to [Amy Brandon](#) and [Rita Torres](#) for all their hard work in organising such a mammoth event! See you there! 🙌 Centre for Music and Audio Technology ICMP London - The Institute of Contemporary Music Performance <https://www.21cguitar.com/livestream...>

 Sam Cave
23 March · 🌐

Yesterday was the first day of the wonderful 21st Century Guitar conference. It was a fantastic first day with many extremely interesting lectures, presentations and performances. Looking forward to today - microtonality and extended techniques day. Tomorrow I will give a lecture-recital about Radulescu's amazing music! Check out the live feed here...

 Sam Cave
24 March · 🌐

If anyone is free at 2pm today I'm giving a lecture-recital about Radulescu's amazing music at this unbelievable conference! Huge congratulations to [Amy Brandon](#) and [Rita Torres](#) and everyone involved in organising this event!

[Divine Art Recordings Group](#)

 Kate Lewis is with **Amy Brandon** and **Rita Torres**.
22 March · 🌐

Guitarists and guitar research friends --- check out an incredible line-up of live-streamed performances, panels and round-table discussions happening all this week.

Rita Torres
26 March · 🌐

A short while ago, [Amy Brandon](#) and I closed [The 21st Century Guitar Conference 2021](#). We had five full days of amazing lectures and performances centred on the topic "Unconventional approaches to performance, composition and research".

I thank all those who contributed to the conference and advertised it. I am especially grateful for the support of [CESEM - Centro de Estudos de Sociologia e Estética Musical](#) and the International Guitar Research Centre, which made possible the joint keynotes by [Caroline Delume & Pascale Criton](#) and [Elena Casoli & Maurizio Pisati](#), as well as the special lectures by [Milton Mermikides](#) and [Steve Goss](#). A special thanks goes to our technical director (and tech freak) [Michelle LaCour](#) (www.michellelacour.com), who, together with Amy, made possible streaming the conference (which ran super smoothly), allowing viewers all around the world to deepen their knowledge on the guitar(s) and its contemporary repertoire and be informed of the latest guitar-related research.

All conference's content is available at www.21cguitar.com. Proceedings should be available in a year.

Thanks Amy for this experience and good luck for 21cguitar 2022!

- Tolgahan Coğulu**
Such a historical event! Congrats and i hope it will continue in the next years 🍷🍷🍷
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Steve Goss**
Well, that was an incredible conference. Where to begin? Amy, Rita, Michelle and everyone else involved have created the most valuable research resource imaginable. The films of the conference will nourish guitar researchers for years to come. I feel truly humbled to have been in a small way involved with this landmark event.
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Andreas Aase**
Fantastic work, Rita, Amy and Michelle!
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Sam Cave**
It was the most amazing week, and an unbelievable achievement! Huge congratulations to you and Amy and Michelle. I am so thrilled and honoured to have been a participant!
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Tom Williams**
What an incredible feat Rita and Amy. Seamless the whole way through and such an enjoyable week. Thanks to all involved
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Fernando López Andújar**
Thanks for this fantastic festival and Congratulations!!
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Michael Ibsen**
Thank you for your work putting this together Rita! I hope we get to meet in person one day soon 😊 If you are ever in the Netherlands let me know.
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Michael Ibsen**
and of course a huge thank you to [Amy Brandon](#) and [Andrew Noseworthy](#) and Michelle and the long list of people who put so much time into making this work!
Like · Reply · 29 w
- Andrew Noseworthy**
and [Michael Ibsen](#) ! meeting and working with you throughout this process was a major highlight! Hope to meet in person someday!
Like · Reply · 29 w

- 75 25 comments 8 shares
- Aaron Larget-Caplan**
Thank you for bringing together such a diverse set of musicians for a wonderful conference. I look forward to meeting people in person in 2022!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Rich Perks**
Congratulations to you both for delivering a fantastic event! And thank you! It was superb!
Like · Reply · 29 w · Edited
 - Steve Cowan**
Incredible week - huge thanks to everyone !
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Joseph Ehrenpreis**
A titanic feat! Excellent job and congratulations Rita Torres and Amy Brandon
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Caroline Delume**
Thank you Rita Torres and Amy Brandon for such an amazing conference
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Elena Casoli**
Thanks you Rita and Amy for this great week and congratulations! It has been a pleasure to have been participant and thanks to all for the fantastic per lectures and performances!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Hugo Simões**
Muitos parabéns! Foi fantástico. 😊
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Marc Estibeiro**
Just fabulous!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Marco Ramelli**
Congratulations to you both!! it was an incredible event!!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Colton Chapman**
So inspirational that my brain still hurts. Thank you and everyone involved on the logistics side for putting this together. Hope the aliens of 3000 make good use of this documentation.
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Amy Brandon**
Colton Chapman It's true, who knows what extended techniques aliens may be capable of
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Michael Ibsen**
Andrew Noseworthy can't wait for that day 😊
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Jorge Sad Levi**
Felicitaciones!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Andrew Noseworthy**
Sent many emails leading up to the conference that ended with "thanks so much for all you do", and plan to send another soon, but will echo that statement again here! Thanks for all your impeccable work Rita Torres and Amy Brandon, (and Michelle hiding... See more
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Pascale Criton**
Thank you so much Rita Torres and Amy Brandon for making possible this great meeting, formidably thought and conducted. So many aspects discussed will make us think the future... Merci!
Like · Reply · 29 w
 - Rita Torres**
Pascale Criton thank you so much for your contribution!
Like · Reply · 29 w